

DEVELOPMENT OF TECHNOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF COATING THE STAMP SURFACE WITH CEMENTITE ALLOY

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Abstract. This article describes that one of the ways to increase the life of stamps is to research on increasing the life of stamps through getting a cementite coating.

Key words: *cementite coating, galvanic, quality of the electrolyte, electrochemical equivalent, analytical balance, diffusion capacity, Galvanic bath.*

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Introduction

There are types of cementing with solid, liquid and gas carburators [1]. Cementing in a liquid carburator is universal and technically the simplest. The parts are placed in a box with a carburator and placed in the oven for heating. The rate of carbonization based on pistachio coal in a solid carburator increases if 5...20% nitrate-cementite is added to its composition. The increase in the rate of cementation is explained by the interaction of nitrate-cementite with pistachio coal at the saturation temperature, in which a more effective gaseous compound is formed, which accelerates carbon diffusion to the metal surface [3].

Despite the simplicity of implementation and the results are not bad, the use of cementing in a solid carburator is limited because the process cannot be automated, that is, it is too complicated, manual loading, extraction and cleaning of details, manual to follow the sanitary and hygienic standard. additional difficulties arise. Therefore, this method is approved for individual production.

Solid carburizer is made from a mixture of barium-carbonate, calcium carbonate, etc. in independent pistachio coal in centralized or machine-building enterprises (GOST 2407-83), mixtures are added in the amount of up to 15% [4].

The holding time in the furnace at a temperature of 900...950°C depends on the depth of the layer to be cemented, and is from 3 to 12 hours. At this time, the depth of saturation reaches from 0.25 to 1.4 mm. Also, cementing method by adding boron carbonate, calcium carbonate or sodium, sand and other fillers is also used in the carburator.

In a liquid carburator, cementation is carried out with diluted salts in a bath. The basis of the liquid mixture is calcined soda Na_2CO_3 (83...84%), table salt NaCl (8...10%), silicon carbide SiC (7...8%) and others. The duration of cementation is 1 to 2 hours. Applying ultrasonic waves to the mixture increases the cementing layer by 2...2.5 times compared to ordinary liquid cementing.[2]

Thus, cementation in a liquid carburizer differs in high productivity due to rapid heating of parts and high activity of the carburizer, which reduces the cost of the process of diffusion saturation of metal.

But liquid cementing has its own disadvantages:

- operation of liquid baths is more complicated than chamber ovens;
- strict requirements for safety equipment;
- rapid depletion of carbon in the liquid bath, which leads to frequent replacement of the carburator.

Therefore, this technology is not widely used and is mainly used for small details.

Method

We used a 2.5-liter bath in laboratory conditions to study the impact of cementite coating technology on product quality. The composition of electrolytes and deposition modes is presented in the table.

Table 1.

Electrolysis composition and coating mode

No	Electrolyte composition and coverage modes	g/l
1	Cementite sulfate (metal for)	35
2	chalky acid	30
3	Potassium chloride	7
4	Temperature , °C	10 -55
5	Cathodic flow density , A/dm ²	60

During the experiments, information was obtained on the effect of various technological factors on the process of galvanic coating of cementite sulfate alloy. The composition and quality of alloy coatings were determined depending on the cementite concentration in the electrolyte and the electrolysis mode (electrolyte current density, temperature) with a constant cementite concentration of 30 g/l. In all experiments, the concentration of salts (g/l) is equal to: boric acid-30; potassium chloride-7; potassium chloride serves in the electrolyte to increase the electrical conductivity of the solution, as well as to increase the rate of coating of cementite anodes with a low rate of coverage. Boric acid is added to improve the quality of the electrolyte.

The amount of cementite in the electrolyte has a significant effect on the quality of the coating, to increase the hardness of the working surface of the stamps, the roughness of the surface.

A cementite plate was used as an anode. It is required to produce an electrolyte from a metal ion, and it should not exceed 3-5% of the weight of the covered part. During processing, metal and electrolysis composition were compared with chemical analysis. The surface quality of the coating was monitored by scanning electron microscope model 52316-12. The change in the metal content depending on the current was calculated using the formula (1).

$$BT = \frac{m_{spl} \cdot E_{Cu}}{m_{Cu} \cdot E_{spl}} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

in this

m_{Cu} - nulocometer weight during coating, g.

E_{Cu} - the electrochemical equivalent of cementite, $g / A \cdot u$.

m_{cni} - weight of the main cathode, g.

E_{spl} - electrochemical equivalent in the alloy, $g / A \cdot u$.

The accuracy of the weight of the main cathode is 0.0001 g. was measured on an analytical balance. The current was measured on an electromagnetic system milliammeter with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$.

The electrochemical equivalent composition was calculated using the formula (2):

$$q_{cni} = \frac{q_{Co}}{q_{Co} + x_{Co}} \quad (2)$$

where, q_{Co} is the electrochemical equivalent of cementite.

x_{Co} - the mass of cementite in the alloy.

Formula (3) was used to calculate the average coverage of the coating being coated

$$\delta = \frac{m \cdot 10^4}{S \cdot \rho} \quad (3)$$

where, m – the cathode coverage value, g .

S – surface to be covered, cm^2 .

ρ – coating density, g/cm^3 .

The coating density was determined using the following formula (4).

$$\rho = \rho_{Co} X_{Co} \quad (4)$$

in this, ρ_{Co} - respectively, the density of cementite, g/cm^3 .

X_{Co} - the mass of cementite, respectively. g .

The formula for determining the speed of detail surface coverage

$$v = \frac{\delta}{\tau} \quad (5)$$

where, δ – the coating thickness, mm .

τ – electrolysis time, h .

The duration of electrolysis (6) is calculated by the formula:

$$\tau = \frac{\delta \cdot \rho_{spl}}{E_{spl} \cdot BT \cdot i_k} \quad (6)$$

where, i_k - the current density at the cathode, A/dm^2 .

The diffusion capacity of the electrolytes was carried out in a cell with a ratio of the length to the width of the cathode space of five parts. The diffusion capacity of electrolytes is calculated by the following formula

$$PC = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^5 |a_n - b_n|}{3,185} \cdot 100\% \quad (7)$$

where a_n - primary current distribution

b_n - secondary current distribution

Table 2 for a five-part cell in the primary distribution $l/h=2,35$

Table 2.

No	1	2	3	4	5
a_n	2.18	1,415	0.755	0.4	0.255

Based on this table $\sum |1-a_n| = 3,185$

$$b_n = \frac{\Delta m_n}{\Delta m_{sr}} \quad (8)$$

in which Δm_n - coated metal mass.

$$\Delta m_{sr} = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{n=1}^5 \Delta m_n \quad (9)$$

n – number of sections ($n=5$).

In the conditions of application of the galvanic method, mandatory conditions are applied to the components of the coating. The alloy is selected as dependent variables in the modeling of the galvanic process: the amount of cementite in the electrolyte, the temperature of the electrolyte. Full factors were used in the research process. This method also makes it possible to evaluate the interaction factors in the composition of the alloy.

Three parallel determinations were averaged for each parameter value (cementite content present in the alloy).

A regression equation for full factors was used in the experiment and it had the following form.

$$Y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_{12}x_1x_2 \quad (10)$$

Based on the data of the study, regression coefficients were obtained and checked.

Using the calculated formulas, it is possible to control the composition of the alloy according to the composition of the electrolyte, the current density and the temperature of the electrolyte.

The effect of cementite alloy on the electrodeposition process was carried out in a special installation (Fig. 3). It consists of two coils connected in parallel to the power source and located on either side of the Galvanic bath. The coils are fitted with steel "S" shaped cores, which also serve as a support for the coils. When the coils are connected to a voltage source, an alternating or constant magnetic field is created between them, depending on the current source

Figure 1. Scheme of the electromagnetic device

1-metal device, 2-electric coil, 3-special research tank (bath), 4-cathode plate .

Result

This suggests that the hardness of the stamp surface after coating has a decisive effect on the amount of corrosion when testing coatings in electrolysis. Figure 2. shows a graphical interpretation of the hardness of the wear of stamps during operation, which is represented by a linear relationship. It is not difficult to optimize the process in sulfate-fluorine electrolyte. The above conditions are carried out with a temperature of 45-50 0C and a cathode density Dk of 60-70. The choice of process conditions becomes difficult due to the fact that the regimes that provide sufficiently high corrosion resistance of coatings in fluorine-silicofluoride electrolyte are not optimal from the point of view of performance.

Figure 1 Comparison diagram of obtained theoretical and practical results

Figure 3. Hardness of the stamp before galvanic coating.

Therefore, the selection of the most accurate modes is carried out based on the practical requirements imposed by the operating conditions of the parts.

The study of the corrosion resistance of the cementite coating under different specific loads determines the compaction, adjustment and surface cleanliness (Fig.3).

Figure 4. Hardness of the stamp after galvanic coating with cementite.

Conclusion

There are several ways to increase the life of stamps, one of the most effective of which is to get a cementite coating.

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